

Multi-modal Place Classification for Semantic Robot Localization

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Multi-modal Place Classification for Semantic Robot Localization*

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*A preliminary version of part of the experimental evaluation reported in this work was presented in [Pronobis et al., 2008].

Abstract

The ability to localize itself in the world is crucial for a mobile robot. To this end, topological and semantic descriptions are gaining popularity for augmenting purely metric space representations. Indoor environments are particularly suited to this approach, as their structure allows us to think about space in terms of rooms and places very intuitively. Moreover, different places can be classified as corridors, offices, kitchens, etc., due to their functionality. In this paper we propose an algorithm that allows a mobile robot to semantically localize itself in an indoor environment. We present a multi-modal place classification system able to identify places and recognize semantic categories. The system effectively utilizes information from different robotic sensors by fusing multiple visual cues and laser range data. This is achieved using a high-level cue integration scheme based on a Support Vector Machine that learns how to optimally combine and weight each cue. Our multi-modal place classification approach can be used to obtain a real-time semantic space labeling system which integrates information over time and space. We perform an extensive experimental evaluation of the method for two different platforms and environments, on a realistic off-line database and in a live experiment on an autonomous robot. The results clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of our cue integration scheme and its value for robust place classification under varying conditions.

1 Introduction

The most fundamental competence for an autonomous agent, such as a mobile robot, is to know its position in the world. This can be represented in terms of raw metric coordinates, topological location, or even semantic description. Recently, there has been a growing interest in augmenting (or even replacing) purely metric space representations with topological and semantic place information. Several attempts have been made to build autonomous cognitive agents able to perform human-like tasks [CoSy; COGNIRON]. Enhancing the space

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8 representation to be more meaningful from the point of view of spatial reasoning and human-
9 robot interaction have been at the forefront of the issues being addressed [Zender et al., 2008;
10 Kuipers, 2006; Topp and Christensen, 2006]. Indeed, in the concrete case of indoor environ-
11 ments, the ability to understand the existing topological relations and associate semantic
12 terms like “corridor” or “office” with places, gives a much more intuitive idea of the position
13 of the robot than global metric coordinates. Additionally, the semantic information about
14 places can extend the capabilities of a robot in other tasks such as localization [Rottmann
15 et al., 2005], exploration [Stachniss et al., 2006], or navigation [Galindo et al., 2005].
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24 Nowadays, robots are usually equipped with several sensors providing both geometrical
25 and visual information about the environment. Historically, early work on place classification
26 relied on sonars and/or laser range data as robust sensory modalities [Martínez Mozos et al.,
27 2007]. However, the advantages of geometric solutions, such as invariance to visual variations
28 and low dimensionality of the processed information, quickly became their weaknesses. The
29 inability to capture many aspects of complex environments leads to the problem of perceptual
30 aliasing [Kuipers and Beeson, 2002] and greatly limits the usefulness of such methods for
31 topological and semantic mapping. Recent advances in vision have made this modality emerge
32 as a natural and viable alternative. Vision provides richer sensory input allowing for better
33 discrimination. Moreover, a large share of the semantic description of a place is encoded
34 in its visual appearance. However, visual information tends to be noisy and difficult to
35 interpret as the appearance of places varies over time due to changing illumination and
36 human activity. At the same time, the visual variability within place classes is huge, making
37 the semantic mapping a challenging and unsolved problem. Clearly, each modality has its
38 own characteristics. Interestingly, the weaknesses of one often correspond to the strengths of
39 the other.
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56 In this paper, we propose an approach to the place classification and semantic space la-
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8 being problems which combines the stability of geometrical solutions with the versatility of
9 vision. First, we present a recognition system implemented on a mobile robot platform inte-
10 grating multiple cues and modalities. The system is able to perform robust place classification
11 under different types of variations that occur in indoor environments over a span of time of
12 several months. This comprises variations in illumination conditions and in configuration of
13 furniture and small objects. The system relies on different types of visual information pro-
14 vided by global and local descriptors and on geometric cues derived from laser range scans.
15 For the vision channel we apply the Scale-invariant Feature Transform (SIFT, [Lowe, 2004])
16 and Composed Receptive Fields Histograms (CRFH, [Linde and Lindeberg, 2004]). For the
17 laser channel we use the features proposed by Martínez Mozos et al. [2007].

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19 We combine the cues using a new high-level accumulation scheme, which builds on our
20 previous work [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007; Nilsback and Caputo, 2004]. We train for each
21 cue a large margin classifier which outputs a set of scores encoding confidence of the decision.
22 Integration is then achieved by feeding the scores to a Support Vector Machine (SVM, [Cris-
23 tianini and Shawe-Taylor, 2000]). Such an approach allows to optimally combine cues, even
24 obtained using different types of models, with a complex, possibly non-linear function. We
25 call this algorithm the SVM-based Discriminative Accumulation Scheme (SVM-DAS).
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29 Finally, we show how to build a self-contained semantic space labeling system, which relies
30 on multi-modal place classification as one of its components. The system is implemented as
31 a part of an integrated cognitive robotic architecture [CoSy; CAST] and runs on-line on
32 a mobile robot platform. While the robot explores the environment, the system acquires
33 evidences about the semantic category of the current area produced by the place classification
34 component and accumulates them both over time and space. As soon as the system is
35 confident about its decision, the area is assigned a semantic label. We integrate the system
36 with a Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithm and show how a metric
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8 and topological space representation can be augmented with a semantic description.
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10 We evaluated the robustness of the presented methods in several sets of extensive ex-
11 periments. We conducted experiments on two different robot platforms, in two different
12 environments and for two different scenarios. First, we run a series of off-line experiments
13 of increasing difficulty on the IDOL2 database [Luo et al., 2006] to precisely measure the
14 performance of the place classification algorithm in presence of different types of variations.
15 These ranged from short-term visual variations caused by changing illumination to long-term
16 changes which occurred in the office environment over several months. Second, we run a live
17 experiment where a robot performs SLAM and semantic labeling in a new environment using
18 prebuilt models of place categories. Results show that integrating different visual cues, as well
19 as different modalities, allows to greatly increase the robustness of the recognition system,
20 achieving high accuracy under severe dynamic variations. Moreover, the place classification
21 system, when used in the framework of semantic space labeling, can yield a perfectly correct
22 semantic representation even for a new, unknown environment.
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36 The rest of the paper is organized as follows: after a review of the relevant literature
37 (Section 2), Section 3 presents the main principle behind our multi-modal place classifica-
38 tion algorithm and describes the methods used to extract each cue. Then, Section 4 gives
39 details about the new cue integration scheme and Section 5 describes the architecture of
40 the semantic labeling system. Finally, Section 6 presents detailed experimental evaluation
41 of the place classification system and Section 7 reports results of the live experiment with
42 semantic labeling of space. The paper concludes with a summary and possible avenues for
43 future research.
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2 Related Work

Place classification applied to topological localization and extraction of semantic information is a vastly research topic in the robotic community. Purely geometric solutions based on laser range data have proven to be successful for certain tasks and several approaches were proposed using laser scanners as the only sensors. Buschka and Saffiotti [2002] describe a virtual sensor that is able to identify rooms from range data. Martínez Mozos et al. [2007] applied boosting to features extracted from range data to classify places in indoor environments. However, the limitations of such solutions inspired many researchers to turn towards vision which nowadays becomes tractable in real-time applications. The proposed methods employed either perspective [Torralba et al., 2003; Tamimi and Zell, 2004; Filliat, 2007] or omnidirectional cameras [Gaspar et al., 2000; Blaer and Allen, 2002; Ulrich and Nourbakhsh, 2000; Menegatti et al., 2004; Andreasson et al., 2005; Murillo et al., 2007; Valgren and Lilienthal, 2008]. The main differences between the approaches relate to the way the scene is perceived, and thus the method used to extract characteristic features from the scene. Landmark-based techniques make use of either artificial or natural landmarks in order to extract information about a place. Siagian and Itti [2007] relied on visually distinctive image regions as landmarks. Many other solutions employed local image features, with SIFT being the most frequently applied [Lowe, 2004; Se et al., 2001; Andreasson et al., 2005; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007]. Zivkovic et al. [2005] used the SIFT descriptor to build a topological representation by clustering a graph representing relations between images. Other approaches used the bag-of-words technique [Filliat, 2007; Fraundorfer et al., 2007], the SURF features [Bay et al., 2006; Murillo et al., 2007; Valgren and Lilienthal, 2008], or representation based on information extracted from local patches using Kernel PCA [Tamimi and Zell, 2004]. Global features are also commonly used for place recognition. Torralba et al. [Torralba and Sinha, 2001; Torralba et al., 2003; Torralba, 2003] suggested to use a representation called the

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8 “gist” of a scene, which is a vector of principal components of outputs of a bank of spatially
9 organized filters applied to the image. Other approaches use color histograms [Ulrich and
10 Nourbakhsh, 2000; Blaer and Allen, 2002], gradient orientation histograms [Bradley et al.,
11 2005], eigenspace representation of images [Gaspar et al., 2000], or Fourier coefficients of low
12 frequency image components [Menegatti et al., 2004].
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18 In all these approaches, only one modality (laser or vision) was used for classification.
19 Recently, several authors observed that robustness and efficiency of the recognition system
20 can be improved by combining information provided by different visual cues [Pronobis and
21 Caputo, 2007; Siagian and Itti, 2007; Weiss et al., 2007] or different sensors, such as a camera
22 and a laser range finder [Rottmann et al., 2005; Tapus and Siegwart, 2005; Posner et al., 2007].
23 However, in most cases, the integration scheme is build based on prior knowledge about the
24 character of the data or the cues are integrated at the feature level. In contrast, the method
25 presented in this work learns how to combine and weight the classification outputs, keeping
26 features and therefore the information from different modalities separated.
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38 **3 Multi-modal Place Classification**

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41 This section describes our approach to multi-modal place classification, and the algorithms
42 we propose to this purpose. Our method is fully supervised and assumes that during training,
43 each place (room) is represented by a collection of labeled data which capture its intrinsic
44 visual and geometric properties under various viewpoints, at a fixed time and illumination
45 setting. During testing, the algorithm is presented with data samples acquired in the same
46 places, under roughly similar viewpoints but possibly under different conditions (e.g. illu-
47 mination), and after some time (where the time range goes from some minutes to several
48 months). The goal is to recognize correctly each single data sample provided to the system.
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Figure 1: Architecture of the multi-modal place classification system.

The system presented in this paper is able to perform place classification based on multiple cues extracted from multiple modalities. In particular, we perform experiments with geometrical and appearance-based cues acquired using laser range and visual sensors. The architecture of the system is illustrated in Figure 1. We see that there is a separate path for each cue. We use two different visual cues corresponding to two types of image features (local and global) as well as simple geometrical features extracted from laser range scans. Each path consists of two main building blocks: a feature extractor and a classifier. Thus, separate decisions can be obtained for each of the cues in case only one cue is available. Alternatively, our method could decide when to acquire additional information (e.g. only in difficult cases, [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007]). In cases when several cues are available, the outputs encoding the confidence of the single-cue classifiers are combined using an efficient discriminative accumulation scheme.

The rest of this section motivates the choice of modalities as well as the integration scheme (Section 3.1) and gives details about the algorithms used to extract and classify each of the cues for the vision-based paths (Section 3.2) and laser-based path (Section 3.3). A comprehensive description of the algorithms used for cue integration is given in Section 4.

3.1 Multiple Modalities for Place Classification

The ability to integrate multiple cues, possibly extracted from multiple sensory modalities, is an important feature for a mobile robot. First of all, as each sensor usually captures a different aspect of the environment, using multiple cues allows for obtaining more descriptive representation. A laser range scanner can be a valuable source of geometrical information, while vision is necessary if a robot requires notion of human-like appearance-based concepts. Good descriptive and discriminative abilities along with robustness are the two crucial features of a place classification system with a great influence on its overall performance. The visual sensor is an irreplaceable source of distinctive information about a place. However, this information tends to be noisy and difficult to analyze due to the susceptibility to variations introduced by changing illumination and everyday activities in the environment. At the same time, most recent robotic platforms are equipped with a laser range scanner which provides much more stable and robust geometric cues. These cues, however, are unable to uniquely represent the properties of different places (perceptual aliasing, [Kuipers and Beeson, 2002]). As a result, problems arise when loops must be closed or the robot needs to perform global localization (the kidnapped robot problem). It is clear, that the performance of the system could be increased if different cues were combined in an efficient manner. At this point, it is important to note that even alternative interpretations of the information obtained by the same sensor can be valuable, which will be experimentally proved in Section 6.

Various cue integration methods have been proposed in the robotics and machine learning community [Tapus and Siegwart, 2005; Nilsback and Caputo, 2004; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007; Poggio et al., 1985; Triesch and Eckes, 1998; Matas et al., 1995]. These approaches can be described according to various criteria. For instance, Clark and Yuille [1990] suggest to classify them into two main groups, *weak coupling* and *strong coupling*. Assuming that each cue is used as input of a different classifier, weak coupling is when the output of two

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8 or more independent classifiers are combined. Strong coupling is instead when the output
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10 of one classifier is affected by the output of another classifier, so that their outputs are
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12 not anymore independent. Another possible classification is into *low level* and *high level*
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14 integration methods, where the emphasis is on the level at which integration happens. We
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16 call *low level integration methods* those algorithms where cues are combined together at the
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18 feature level, and then used as input to a single classifier. This approach has been used
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20 successfully for object recognition using multiple visual cues [Matas et al., 1995], and for
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22 topological mapping using multiple sensor modalities [Tapus and Siegwart, 2005]. In spite
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24 of remarkable performances for specific tasks, there are two main drawbacks of the low level
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26 methods. First, if one of the cues gives misleading information, it is quite probable that the
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28 new feature vector will be adversely affected influencing the whole performance. Second, we
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30 can expect the dimension of such a feature vector to increase as the number of cues grows, and
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32 each of the cues needs to be used even if one would allow for correct classification. This implies
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34 longer learning and recognition times, greater memory requirements and possibly curse of
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36 dimensionality effects. Another strategy is to keep the cues separated and to integrate the
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38 outputs of individual classifiers, each trained on a different cue [Poggio et al., 1985; Nilsback
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40 and Caputo, 2004; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007]. We call such algorithms *high level integration*
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42 *methods*, of which voting is the most popular [Duda et al., 2001]. These techniques are more
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44 robust with respect to noisy cues or sensory channels and allow to decide on the number of
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46 cues that should be extracted and used for each particular classification task [Pronobis and
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48 Caputo, 2007].
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51 In this paper, we focus on a weak coupling, high level integration method called *accumu-*
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53 *lation*. The underlying idea is that information from different cues can be summed together,
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55 thus accumulated. The idea was first proposed in probabilistic framework by Poggio et al.
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57 [1985] and further explored by Aloimonos and Shulman [1989]. The method was then ex-
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8 tended to discriminative methods in [Nilsback and Caputo, 2004; Pronobis and Caputo,
9 2007].

13 3.2 Vision-based Place Classification

16 As a basis for the vision-based channel, we used the place recognition system presented
17 in [Pronobis et al., 2006; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007], which is built around a Support
18 Vector Machine (SVM) classifier [Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor, 2000] and two types of visual
19 features, global and local, extracted from the same image frame. In order to extract the
20 global features, we applied a rich global descriptor, Composed Receptive Field Histograms
21 (CRFH) [Linde and Lindeberg, 2004]. Distinctive local features were obtained using the
22 SIFT descriptor [Lowe, 2004]. Both have already been proved successful in the domain of
23 vision-based localization [Pronobis et al., 2006; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007; Se et al., 2001].

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25 CRFHs are a sparse multi-dimensional statistical representation of responses of several
26 image filters applied to the input image. Following Pronobis et al. [2006], we used histograms
27 of 6 dimensions, with 28 bins per dimension, computed from second order normalized Gaus-
28 sian derivative filters applied to the illumination channel at two scales. The SIFT descriptor
29 instead represents local image patches around interest points characterized by coordinates in
30 the scalespace in the form of histograms of gradient directions. In order to find the coordi-
31 nates of the interest points, we used a scale and affine invariant region detector based on the
32 difference-of-Gaussians (DoG) operator [Rothganger et al., 2006].

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34 We used SVMs for creating models from both visual cues. A review of the theory behind
35 SVMs can be found in Section 4.1. In case of SVMs, special care must be taken in choosing
36 an appropriate kernel function. In this work, we used the χ^2 kernel [Chapelle et al., 1999]
37 for the global CRFH descriptors, and the match kernel proposed by Wallraven et al. [2003]
38 for the local SIFT descriptors. Both have been used in our previous work on SVM-based
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8 place recognition, obtaining good performances. Summarizing, we constructed 2 different
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10 single-cue models based on the information acquired with the visual sensor. We shall refer
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12 to them as CRFH and SIFT in the rest of the paper.

13 14 15 16 **3.3 Laser-based Place Classification**

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18 In addition to the visual channel, we used a laser range sensor for semantic place classification.
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20 A single 2D laser scan covered a field of view of 180° in front of the robot. A laser observation
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22 $z = \{b_0, \dots, b_{M-1}\}$ contains a set of beams b_i , in which each beam b_i consists of a tuple (α_i, d_i) ,
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24 where α_i is the angle of the beam relative to the robot and d_i is the length of the beam.
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26 For each laser observation, we calculated a set of simple geometric features represented
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28 by single real values. These features are standard geometrical features often used in shape
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30 analysis and pattern recognition. The features were introduced for place classification by
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32 Martínez Mozos et al. [2007] where laser observations covering a 360° field of view were used.
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34 The complete set of features consists of two subsets. The first subset contains geometrical
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36 features calculated directly from the laser beams. The second subset comprises geometrical
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38 features extracted from a polygon approximation of the laser observation. This polygon is
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40 created by connecting the end points of the beams. The selection of features is based on the
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42 results presented in [Martínez Mozos et al., 2007].
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45 As classifiers for the laser-based channel, we tried both AdaBoost [Freund and Schapire,
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47 1995], following the work in [Martínez Mozos et al., 2007], and SVMs. In the rest of the
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49 paper, we will refer to the two laser-based models as L-AB and L-SVM, respectively. For the
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51 geometric features, we used a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel [Cristianini and Shawe-
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53 Taylor, 2000] with SVMs, which we selected through a set of reference experiments. Both
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55 classifiers were benchmarked on the laser-based place classification task. Results presented
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57 in Section 6.2 show an advantage of the more complex SVM classifier.
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4 Discriminative Cue Integration

This section describes our approach to cue integration from one or multiple modalities. We propose an SVM-based Discriminative Accumulation Scheme (SVM-DAS), a technique performing non-linear cue integration by discriminative accumulation. For each cue, we train a separate large margin classifier which outputs a set of scores (outputs), encoding the confidence of the decision. We achieve integration by feeding the scores to an SVM. Compared to previous accumulation methods [Poggio et al., 1985; Caputo and Dorko, 2002; Nilsback and Caputo, 2004; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007], SVM-DAS gives several advantages: (a) discriminative accumulation schemes achieve consistently better performances than probabilistic ones [Poggio et al., 1985; Caputo and Dorko, 2002], as shown in [Nilsback and Caputo, 2004]; (b) compared to previous discriminative accumulation schemes [Nilsback and Caputo, 2004; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007], our approach accumulates cues with a more complex, possibly non-linear function, by using the SVM framework and kernels [Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor, 2000]. Such approach makes it possible to integrate outputs of different classifiers such as SVM and AdaBoost. At the same time, it learns the weights for each cue very efficiently, therefore making it possible to accumulate large numbers of cues without computational problems.

In the rest of the section we first sketch the theory behind SVMs (Section 4.1), a crucial component in our approach. We then describe the Generalized Discriminative Accumulation Scheme (G-DAS, Pronobis and Caputo [2007], Section 4.2) on which to a large extent we build. Finally, we introduce the new algorithm and discuss its advantages in Section 4.3.

4.1 Support Vector Machines

Consider the problem of separating the set of labeled training data $(\mathbf{x}_1, y_1), (\mathbf{x}_2, y_2), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_n, y_n)$ into two classes, where $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathfrak{R}^N$ is a feature vector and $y_i \in$

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8 $\{-1, +1\}$ its class label. Assuming that the two classes can be separated by a hyperplane in
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10 some Hilbert space \mathcal{H} , then the optimal separating hyperplane is the one which has maximum
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12 distance to the closest points in the training set resulting in a discriminant function

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) + b.$$

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18 The classification result is then given by the sign of $f(\mathbf{x})$. The values of α_i and b are found
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20 by solving a constrained minimization problem, which can be done efficiently using the SMO
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22 algorithm [Platt, 1999]. Most of the α_i 's take the value of zero; those \mathbf{x}_i with nonzero α_i
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24 are the "support vectors". In case where the two classes are non-separable, the optimization
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26 is formulated in such way that the classification error is minimized and the final solution
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28 remains identical. The mapping between the input space and the usually high dimensional
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30 feature space \mathcal{H} is done using kernels $K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x})$.

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32 The extension of SVM to multi class problems can be done in several ways. Here we will
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34 mention three approaches used throughout the paper:

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37 1. *Standard one-against-all (OaA) strategy.* If M is the number of classes, M SVMs are
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39 trained, each separating a single class from all other classes. The decision is then based
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41 on the distance of the classified sample to each hyperplane, and the sample is assigned
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43 to the class corresponding to the hyperplane for which the distance is largest.
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46 2. *Modified one-against-all strategy.* In [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007], a modified version
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48 of the OaA principle was proposed. The authors suggested to use distances to precom-
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50 puted average distances of training samples to the hyperplanes (separately for each of
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52 the classes), instead of the distances to the hyperplanes directly. In this case, the sam-
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54 ple is assigned to the class corresponding to the hyperplane for which the distance is
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56 smallest. Experiments presented in this paper and in [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007] show
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58 that in many applications this approach outperforms the standard OaA technique.
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3. *One-against-one (OaO) strategy.* In this case, $M(M - 1)/2$ two-class machines are trained for each pair of classes. The final decision can then be taken in different ways, based on the $M(M - 1)/2$ outputs. A popular choice is to consider as output of each classifier the class label and count votes for each class; the test image is then assigned to the class that received more votes.

Support Vector Machines do not provide any out-of-the-box solution for estimating confidence of the decision; however, it is possible to derive confidence information and hypotheses ranking from the distances between the samples and the hyperplanes. In the work presented in this paper, we applied the distance-based methods proposed in [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007], which define confidence as a measure of unambiguity of the final decision.

4.2 Generalized Discriminative Accumulation Scheme

The Generalized Discriminative Accumulation Scheme (G-DAS) was proposed first in [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007], as a more effective generalization of the algorithm presented in [Nilsback and Caputo, 2004]. It accumulates multiple cues, possibly different modalities, by turning classifiers into experts. The basic idea is to consider real-valued outputs of a multi-class discriminative classifier (e.g. SVM) as an indication of a soft decision for each class. Then, all the outputs obtained from the various cues are summed together, therefore linearly accumulated. Specifically, suppose we are given M classes and, for each class, a set of n_j training samples $\{\mathbf{I}_i^j\}_{i=1}^{n_j}$, $j = 1, \dots, M$. Suppose also that, from each sample, we extract a set of P different cues $\{T_p(\mathbf{I}_i^j)\}_{p=1}^P$. The goal is to perform recognition using all of them. The G-DAS algorithm consists of two steps:

1. *Single-cue Models.* From the original training set $\{\{\mathbf{I}_i^j\}_{i=1}^{n_j}\}_{j=1}^M$, containing samples belonging to all M classes, define P new training sets $\{\{T_p(\mathbf{I}_i^j)\}_{i=1}^{n_j}\}_{j=1}^M$, $p = 1, \dots, P$, each relative to a single cue. For each new training set train a multi-class classifier.

Figure 2: A real example of test image misclassified by using a single cue, but classified correctly by using G-DAS.

Then, given a test sample \mathbf{I} , for each single-cue classifier estimate a set of outputs $\{O_h^p(T_p(\mathbf{I}))\}_{h \in H}$ reflecting the relation of the sample to the model. In case of the SVMs with standard OaO and OaA multi-class extensions, the outputs would be values of the $M(M-1)/2$ or M discriminant functions $f_h^p(T_p(\mathbf{I}))$ learned by the SVM algorithm during training.

2. *Discriminative Accumulation.* After all the outputs are computed for all the cues, combine them with different weights by a linear function:

$$O_h^{\Sigma P}(\mathbf{I}) = \sum_{p=1}^P a_p O_h^p(T_p(\mathbf{I})), \quad a_p \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

The final decision can be estimated with any method commonly used for multi-class, single cue SVM.

An important property of accumulation is the ability to perform correct classification even when each of the single cues gives misleading information. This behavior is illustrated on a real example in Figure 2. Despite these advantages, G-DAS presents some potential limitations: first, it uses only one weight for all outputs of each cue. This simplifies the parameter estimation process (usually, an extensive search is performed to find the coefficients $\{a_p\}_{p=1}^P$), but also constraints the ability of the algorithm to adapt to the properties of each single cue. Second, accumulation is obtained via a linear function, which might not be

sufficient in case of complex problems. The next section shows how our new accumulation scheme, SVM-DAS, addresses these issues.

4.3 SVM-based Discriminative Accumulation Scheme

The Support Vector Machines-based Discriminative Accumulation Scheme (SVM-DAS) accumulates the outputs generated by single-cue classifiers by using a more complex, possibly non-linear function. The outputs are used as an input to an SVM, and the parameters of the integration function are learned during the optimization process, for instance using the SMO algorithm [Platt, 1999]. These characteristics address the potential drawbacks of G-DAS discussed in the previous section.

More specifically, the new SVM-DAS accumulation function is given by:

$$O_k^{\Sigma P}(\mathbf{I}) = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i^k y_i K(\mathbf{O}_i, \mathbf{O}) + b^k, \quad k = 1, \dots, K,$$

where \mathbf{O} is a vector containing all the outputs for all cues:

$$\mathbf{O} = [\{O_h^1(T_1(\mathbf{I}))\}_{h \in H_1}, \dots, \{O_h^P(T_P(\mathbf{I}))\}_{h \in H_P}].$$

The parameters α_i^k , y_i , and the support vectors \mathbf{O}_i are inferred from the training data either directly or efficiently during the optimization process. The number of the final outputs K and the way of obtaining the final decision depends on the multi-class extension used with SVM-DAS. We use the one-against-one extension throughout the paper for which $K = M(M-1)/2$.

The nonlinearity is given by the choice of the kernel function, thus in the case of the linear kernel the method is still linear. In this sense, SVM-DAS is more general than G-DAS, while it preserves all its important properties (e.g. the ability to give correct results for two misleading cues, see Figure 2). Also, for SVM-DAS each of the integrated outputs depends on all the outputs from single-cue classifiers, and the coefficients are learned optimally. Note

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8 that the outputs O_h^p can be derived from a combination of different large margin classifiers,
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10 and not only from SVM.

11 12 13 14 **5 Place Classification for Semantic Space Labeling** 15 16

17 One of the applications of a place classification system is semantic labeling of space. This
18 section provides a brief overview of the problem and describes how we employed our multi-
19 modal place classification method to build a semantic labeling system. We evaluated the
20 system in a live experiment described in Section 7.
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25 26 27 **5.1 Semantic Labeling of Space** 28

29 The problem of semantic labeling can be described as assigning meaningful semantic descrip-
30 tions (e.g. “corridor” or “kitchen”) to areas in the environment. Typically, semantic labeling
31 is used as a way of augmenting the internal space representation with additional information.
32 This can be used by the agent to enhance communication with a human user or to reason
33 about space. A term which needs to be clarified is an area. On a finer scale, in indoor
34 environments, different semantic descriptions can be used e.g. for parts of a single room in
35 order to reflect their specific functionality. Dining area and sink area of a kitchen can be an
36 example. However, in case of most typical environments, it is sufficient to distinguish be-
37 tween semantic categories which are usually associated with rooms e.g. “office” or “corridor”
38 [Zender et al., 2007].
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50 As it will be shown through experiments in Sections 6 and 7, the place classification system
51 described in this paper can yield a place class with high accuracy given a single sample of
52 multi-modal data (e.g. one image and laser scan). However, when used for semantic labeling,
53 the algorithm is requested to provide a label for the whole area under exploration. At the
54 same time, the system must be resilient and able to deal with such problems as temporary lack
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Figure 3: Architecture of the semantic space labeling system based on place classification.

of informative cues, continuous stream of similar information or long-term occlusions. Given that the system is operating on a mobile robot, it is allowed to use crude information about its movement provided by the wheel encoders. This information should be used to ensure robustness to the typical variations that occur in the environment but also to the problems mentioned above. Finally, the system should be able to measure its own confidence and restrain from making a decision until some confidence level is reached. All these assumptions and requirements have been taken into consideration while designing the system described in the following section.

5.2 Architecture of the System

The architecture of our system is presented in Figure 3. The system relies on three sensors typically found on a mobile robot platform: a monocular camera, a single 2D laser scanner, and wheel encoders. The images from the camera, together with the laser scans are used as an input for the multi-modal place classification component. For each pair of data samples, place classification provides its beliefs about the semantic category to which the samples belong.

Figure 4: Illustration of the spatio-temporal accumulation process. As the robot explores the environment, the beliefs collected on the way accumulate over time within the bin corresponding to the current pose (x, y, θ) and over space in different bins.

These beliefs are encoded in the integrated outputs as discussed in Section 4. Moreover, the confidence of the decision is also measured and provided by the classification component.

A labeling system should provide a robust and stable output for the whole areas in the environment. Since the sensors employed are not omni-directional, it is necessary to accumulate and fuse information over time. Moreover, the data that the robot gathers are not evenly spread over different viewpoints. On the contrary, in many cases the sensors receive a continuous stream of non-informative data. As a possible solution, we propose to use a confidence-based spatio-temporal accumulation method. The principle behind the method is illustrated in Figure 4. As the robot explores the environment, it moves with a varying speed. The robot has information about its own movement (odometry) provided by the wheel encoders. As errors accumulate over time, this information can only be used to estimate relative movement rather than absolute position. This is sufficient for our application. The spatio-temporal accumulation process creates a sparse histogram along the robot pose trajectory described by the metric position (x, y) and heading (θ) as shown in Figure 4. The pose is estimated based on the odometry information and thus is reliable only locally.

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8 The size of the histogram bins are adjusted so that each bin roughly corresponds to a sin-
9 gular viewpoint. Then, as the robot moves, the beliefs about the current semantic category
10 accumulate within the bins as in case of G-DAS (with equal weights). This is what we call
11 the temporal accumulation. It prevents a single viewpoint from becoming dominant due
12 to long-term observation. Since each viewpoint observed by the robot will correspond to a
13 different bin, performing accumulation across the bins (this time spatially) allows to gener-
14 ate the final outputs to which each viewpoint contributes equally. In order to exclude most
15 of the misclassifications before they get accumulated, we filter the decisions based on the
16 confidence value provided by the place classification component. Moreover, as the odometry
17 information is unreliable in the long term, the contents of bins visited a certain amount of
18 viewpoints ago are invalidated.

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31 The accumulation process ensures robustness and stability of the generated label for a
32 single area. However, another mechanism is required to provide the system with information
33 about area boundaries. This is required for the accumulation process not to fuse the beliefs
34 across different areas. Here, we propose two solutions to that problem. As described in the
35 previous sections, we can assume that each room of the environment should be assigned one
36 semantic label. In case of indoor environments, rooms are usually separated by door or other
37 narrow openings. Thus, as one solution, we propose to use a simple laser-based door detector
38 which generates hypotheses about door based on the width of the opening which the robot
39 passes. Such a simple algorithm will surely generate a lot of false positives. However, this
40 does not cause problems in the presented architecture since the place classification algorithm
41 should be able to provide correct labeling as in case when two rooms belonging to the same
42 semantic category are connected.

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55 As a second solution, we propose to use another localization and mapping system in order
56 to generate the space representation which will then be augmented with semantic labels. Here
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8 we take the multi-layered approach proposed in [Zender et al., 2008]. The method presented
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10 by Zender et al. [2008] builds a global metric map as the first layer and a navigation graph
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12 as the second. As the robot navigates through the environment, a marker or navigation
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14 node is dropped whenever the robot has traveled a certain distance from the closest existing
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16 node. Nodes are connected following the order in which they were generated. If information
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18 about the current node is provided to the spatio-temporal accumulation process, labels can
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20 be generated for each of the nodes separately. Moreover, as it is possible to detect whether
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22 the robot revisited an existing node, the accumulated information can be saved and used as
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24 a prior the next time the node is visited. For the live experiment described in this paper, we
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26 used the detected doors to bound the areas and navigation graph nodes to keep the priors.
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28 We then propagated the current area label to all the nodes in the area.
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33 6 Experiments with Place Classification

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35 We conducted several series of experiments in order to evaluate the performance of our
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37 place classification system. We tested its robustness to different types of variations, such
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39 as those introduced by changing illumination or human activity over a long period of time.
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41 The evaluation was performed on synchronized visual and laser-range data, acquired using a
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43 mobile robot platform over a time span of 6 months, taken from the IDOL2 database. Details
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45 about the database and experimental setup are given in Section 6.1. Every experiment was
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47 first performed separately for each of the four types of single-cue models (the SVM models
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49 trained on CRFH and SIFT as well as the SVM and AdaBoost models trained on the laser
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51 range cues). Then, the evaluation was repeated for models based on different combinations of
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53 cues and modalities and employing different integration schemes (G-DAS and several variants
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55 of SVM-DAS). We present the results in Section 6.2 and Section 6.3 respectively. We give a
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Figure 5: (a) The mobile robot platform used in the experiments; (b) Map of the environment used during data acquisition and an example laser scan simulated in the corridor. The rooms used during the experiments are annotated.

summary discussion on the efficiency of different solutions in Section 6.4.

6.1 Experimental Setup

The algorithms presented in this paper have been tested on the IDOL2 (Image Database for rObot Localization 2 [Luo et al., 2006]) database. The database was introduced in [Luo et al., 2007] in order to test the robustness of an adaptive visual place recognition system in a real-world dynamic environment observed over a long period of time and under varying illumination conditions. The database comprises 24 image sequences accompanied by laser scans and odometry data acquired using two mobile robot platforms (PeopleBot and PowerBot). The images were captured with a Canon VC-C4 perspective camera using the resolution of 320x240 pixels. In this paper, we will use only the 12 data sequences acquired with the PowerBot, shown in Figure 5a.

The acquisition was performed in a five room subsection of a larger office environment, selected in such way that each of the five rooms represented a different functional area: a one-

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(a) Variations introduced by illumination

(b) Variations observed over time

(c) Remaining rooms (at night)

Figure 6: Examples of pictures taken from the IDOL2 database showing the interiors of the rooms, variations observed over time and caused by activity in the environment as well as introduced by changing illumination.

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8 person office (1pO), a two-persons office (2pO), a kitchen (KT), a corridor (CR), and a printer
9 area (PR). The map of the environment and an example laser scan are shown in Figure 5b.
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11 Example pictures showing interiors of the rooms are presented in Figure 6. The appearance
12 of the rooms was captured under three different illumination conditions: in cloudy weather,
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14 in sunny weather, and at night. The robots were manually driven through each of the five
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16 rooms while continuously acquiring images and laser range scans at a rate of 5fps. Each data
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18 sample was then labelled as belonging to one of the rooms according to the position of the
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20 robot during acquisition. Extension 1 contains a video illustrating the acquisition process of
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22 a typical data sequence in the database. Since the database was originally designed to test
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24 the robustness of place recognition algorithms to variations that occur over a long period
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26 of time, the acquisition process was conducted in two phases. Two sequences were acquired
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28 for each type of illumination conditions over the time span of more than two weeks, and
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30 another two sequences for each setting were recorded 6 months later (12 sequences in total).
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32 Thus, the sequences captured variability introduced not only by illumination but also natural
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34 activities in the environment (presence/absence of people, furniture/objects relocated etc.).
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36 It is important to note that, even for sequences acquired within a short time span under
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38 similar illumination conditions, variations still exist from everyday activities and viewpoint
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40 differences during acquisition. Example images illustrating the captured variability are shown
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42 in Figure 6.
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47 We conducted four sets of experiments, first for each cue separately and then for cues
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49 combined. In order to simplify the experiments with multiple cues, we matched images
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51 with closest laser scans on the basis of the acquisition timestamp. In case of each single
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53 experiment, both training and testing were performed on one data sequence. The first set
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55 consisted of 12 experiments, performed on different combinations of training and test data
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57 acquired closely in time and under similar illumination conditions. For the second set of
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8 experiments, we used 24 pairs of sequences captured still at relatively close times, but under
9 different illumination conditions. In this way, we increased the complexity of the problem
10 [Pronobis et al., 2006; Pronobis and Caputo, 2007]. In the third set of experiments, we tested
11 the robustness of the system to long-time variations introduced by activity in the environment
12 (objects/furniture being moved and reorganized). Therefore, we conducted 12 experiments,
13 where we used for testing data acquired 6 months later, or earlier, than the training data,
14 again under similar illumination conditions. Finally, we combined both types of variations
15 and performed experiments on 24 pairs of training and test sets, obtained 6 months from
16 each other and under different illumination settings. For all experiments, model parameters
17 were determined via cross validation. As a measure of performance we used the percentage
18 of properly classified samples (classification rate) calculated separately for each of the rooms
19 and then averaged with equal weights independently of the number of samples acquired in
20 each room.
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36 6.2 Experiments with Separate Cues

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38 We evaluated the performance of all four types of models: the two SVM models based on
39 visual features (CRFH, SIFT), the AdaBoost and the SVM models trained on the laser range
40 cues (referred to as L-AB and L-SVM). For SVM, we tried the three multi-class extensions
41 described in Section 4.1. The results of all four sets of experiments for these models are
42 presented in Figure 7-10 (the first four bar groups). As a first remark, we see that, according
43 to expectations, the recognition systems based on visual cues (CRFH and SIFT) suffer from
44 changes in illumination, while the geometrical laser-based features don't. Moreover, varia-
45 tions that occurred over a long period of time pose a challenge for both modalities. We can
46 observe differences in performance also between the two visual cues. The models based on
47 global features (CRFH) suffer more from the illumination variations, while the SIFT features
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Figure 7: Classification rates for Exp. 1: stable illumination conditions, close in time.

Figure 8: Classification rates for Exp. 2: varying illumination conditions, close in time.

Figure 9: Classification rates for Exp. 3: stable illumination conditions, distant in time.

Figure 10: Classification rates for Exp. 4: varying illumination conditions, distant in time.

are less robust to variations introduced by human activity in the environment. It is also interesting to note that under stable conditions, the vision-based methods outperform the systems based on laser range cues (95.1% for CRFH and 92.5% for L-SVM). This illustrates the potential of visual cues, but also stresses the need for more robust solutions.

An additional contribution of the paper is the place recognition algorithm based on simple-valued geometrical features and SVMs. Figure 7-10 present a comparison of performance of our new method and the previous solution using the AdaBoost classifier [Martínez Mozos et al., 2007]. We can see that the difference in performance is significant in favor of the SVM-based method (from 6.1% for Exp. 1 to 10.3% for Exp. 4 in average) which allows us to conclude that the robustness of the system was greatly improved by implementing a more complex classifier.

As already mentioned, all the presented experiments with SVMs were repeated for three different multi-class extensions: standard OaO and OaA as well as modified OaA algorithm. The obtained results are in agreement with [Pronobis and Caputo, 2007] - in case of single cue and G-DAS experiments, the modified version gives the best performance independently of the modality on which the classifier was trained.

Figure 11: Distribution of errors made by the four models for each actual class (bright colors indicate errors). The diagonal elements were removed.

A further analysis of the results can be performed, that serves as a motivation for integrating different visual cues and modalities. Figure 11 shows the distribution of errors for each actual class (room) made by the four models. It is apparent that each of the cues makes errors according to a different pattern. At the same time, similarities occur between the same modalities. We can see that visual models are biased towards the corridor, while the geometrical models tend to misclassify places as the printer area. A straightforward explanation can be offered for that phenomenon. The vision-based models were trained on images acquired with perspective camera with constrained viewing angle. As a result, similar visual stimuli coming from the corridor are present in the images captured by the robot leaving each of the rooms. The same area close to a doorway, from the geometrical point of view, is similar to the narrow passage in the printer area. Ideally, the cue integration scheme should learn to treat cues differently, according to the different needs of each class.

6.3 Experiments with Cue Integration

The accumulation schemes presented in this paper perform high level cue integration. As a result, separate models should be trained for each of the combined cues. In our evaluation, we used the models obtained during single-cue experiments. In order to be used for real applications, an integration scheme should perform and generalize well in presence of any

Figure 12: Comparison of performance (classification rates) of SVM-DAS based on different kernel functions for the most complex problem (Exp. 4).

type of variability it might encounter. For that reason, the parameters of the algorithms (weights in case of G-DAS and SVM model in case of SVM-DAS) were always adjusted on the basis of outputs generated during all experiments with single-cue models trained on one particular data sequence. Then, during testing, the previously obtained integration scheme was applied to all experiments with models trained on a different sequence, acquired under similar illumination and closely in time. This way, the generalization abilities of each of the methods were tested in a realistic scenario.

For the final experiments, we selected four different cue accumulation methods: G-DAS and SVM-DAS with three kernel types (linear, RBF, and histogram intersection kernel [Barla et al., 2003]). In all experiments, we found that the SVM-DAS with RBF kernel outperforms the other methods (the difference in performance with respect to G-DAS was statistically significant at the confidence level of 95%). For space reasons, we report results of each of the experiments only using SVM-DAS based on the RBF kernel and G-DAS for comparison (Figure 7-10, last 9 bar groups). A detailed comparison of all variants of SVM-DAS for the

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8 most complex problem (Exp. 4) is given in Figure 12.

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10 We tested the methods with several combinations of different cues and modalities. First,
11 we combined the two visual cues. We see that the generalization of a purely visual recognition
12 system can be greatly improved by integrating different types of cues, in this case local and
13 global. This can be observed especially for Exp. 4, where the algorithms had to tackle the
14 largest variability. Despite that, according to the error distributions in Figure 11, we should
15 expect largest gain when different modalities are combined. As we can see from Figure 7-10
16 this is the case indeed. By combining one visual cue and one laser range cue (e.g. CRFH + L-
17 SVM), we exploit the descriptive power of vision in case of stable illumination conditions and
18 the invariance of geometrical features to the visual noise. Moreover, if the computational cost
19 is not an issue, the performance can be further improved by using both visual cues instead
20 of just one. The gain in this case is statistically significant at the confidence level 95%.
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33 As it was mentioned in Section 4.3, SVM-DAS can be applied for problems where outputs
34 of different classifiers need to be integrated. To test this in practice, we combined the SVM
35 models trained on visual cues with AdaBoost model based on geometrical features (L-AB). We
36 present the results in Figure 7-10 (last bar group). The method obtained large improvement
37 in comparison to each of the individual cues. For instance for Exp. 4, the recognition rate
38 increased by 12.2% in average. This proves the versatility of our approach.
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46 **6.4 Discussion**

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49 The results of the extensive experimental evaluation presented in this section clearly show
50 that SVM-DAS performs significantly better than G-DAS and can be used to integrate out-
51 puts of classifiers of different characteristics employing different multi-class algorithms. We
52 also showed that by using more sophisticated kernel types, it is possible to perform non-linear
53 cue accumulation. The experiments (see Figure 12) show that although there is no drastic
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Cues (Primary cue)	Cue integration method	
	G-DAS	SVM-DAS RBF Kernel
CRFH + SIFT	25.971±18.503	29.453±22.139
CRFH + L-SVM	21.230±20.199	32.736±20.256
SIFT + L-SVM	28.820±20.982	33.344±22.425
SIFT + CRFH + L-SVM	31.858±20.474	40.833±21.916

Table 1: Average percentages (with standard deviations) of test samples for which all cues had to be used in order to obtain the maximal recognition rate.

improvement, we can expect better results with the RBF kernel (especially for the OaO multi-class extension). As a result, we suggest that the kernel was selected according to the constraints put on the computational cost of the solution. Since there are fast implementations of linear SVMs, it might be beneficial to use a linear kernel in cases when the integration scheme must be trained on a very large number of samples. In applications, where only the number of training parameters is an issue, the non-parametric histogram intersection kernel can be used instead of RBF.

At this point, a comment should be made on the computational cost of using multiple cues in general. Although, it is clear that generalization performance can be significantly improved by using multiple cues or modalities, each of the cues introduces additional cost. Therefore, there is always a trade-off between the complexity of the solution and the overall performance. For example, a solution based on global visual features, laser range cues and SVM-DAS runs in real-time at a rate of approximately 5fps, which would not be possible if additional visual cue such as SIFT was used. It should be noted, however, that due to the high level integration architecture, not all of the cues have to be always extracted

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8 and used, especially that, in most cases, decisions based on one cue only are correct. The
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10 computational cost can be significantly reduced by taking the approach presented in [Pronobis
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12 and Caputo, 2007]. By combining confidence estimation methods with cue integration, we
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14 can use additional sources of information only when necessary - when the decision based on
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16 one cue only is not confident enough. This scheme is referred to as Confidence-based Cue
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18 Integration. Table 1 presents the results of applying the scheme to the experiments presented
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20 in this section. We see that, in general, we can base our decision on the fastest model (marked
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22 with bold font in Table 1) and we can retain the maximal performance by using additional
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24 cues only in approximately 30% of cases. Additional cues will be used more often when the
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26 variability is large, and rarely for less difficult cases.
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30 **7 Experiments with Semantic Space Labeling**

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33 We performed an independent live experiment to test our multi-modal semantic space labeling
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35 system running in real-time on a mobile robot platform. The experiment was performed
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37 during working hours in a typical office environment. Both the environment and the robot
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39 platform were different than in case of the off-line evaluation described in Section 6. The
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41 whole experiment was videotaped and a video presenting the setup, experimental procedure
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43 and visualization of the results can be found in Extension 2. The rest of the section gives
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45 details about the experimental setup and the procedure adopted for training the system
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47 (Section 7.1). Then it describes the live experiment and reports obtained results (Section 7.2).
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51 **7.1 Experimental Setup**

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54 The experiment was performed between the 7th and 10th of September 2008 in the building
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56 of the School of Computer Science at the University of Birmingham, Birmingham, United
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58 Kingdom. The interior of the building consists of several office environments located on three
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Figure 13: Examples of images and laser scans (synchronized) taken from the data sequences used for training the models of place classes (a) and acquired during the test run (b) in each of the rooms considered during the experiment. The figure illustrates the within-category variations for corridors and offices as well as other types of variability observed for each place class (e.g. different illumination conditions, activity in the environment).

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8 floors. For our experiments, we selected three semantic categories of rooms that could be
9 found in the building: a corridor, an office and a meeting room. In order to train the system,
10 and build place models for these three classes, we first performed acquisition of training
11 data in different parts of the building. To build the model of an office, we acquired data
12 in three different offices: Aaron's office (1st floor), Robert's office (1st floor) and Richard's
13 office (ground floor). To create a representation of the corridor class, we recorded data in 2
14 corridors, one on the ground floor and one on the 1st floor. The acquisition was performed
15 at night. Finally, to train the model of a meeting room, we used an instance on the 2nd
16 floor. The meeting room belonged to the part of the environment where later we conducted
17 the final test. The data for this class were recorded during the day. A video illustrating the
18 whole data acquisition process is available as Extension 3. The interiors of the rooms can be
19 seen in Figure 13a. The robot was manually driven around each room and data samples were
20 recorded at the rate of 5 fps. All the collected training data are available as Extension 6. In
21 case of the meeting room, corridor on the 1st floor as well as Aaron's and Richard's offices,
22 the acquisition was repeated twice. Examples of images and laser scans acquired in each of
23 the rooms can be found in Figure 13a.

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41 For the real-time experiment, we built the system as described in Section 5. Following the
42 findings of the off-line experiments, we used SVM-DAS with the Gaussian kernel to integrate
43 the classifier outputs for vision and laser range data. For efficiency reasons, we used only
44 global features (CRFH) for the vision channel. We used the one-against-all multi-class SVM
45 extension for the place models. Other parameters were set as described in Section 6.

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51 We trained the place models separately for each modality on a dataset created from one
52 data sequence recorded in each of the rooms. Since one of the advantages of SVM-DAS is the
53 ability to infer the integration function from the training data, after training the models, we
54 trained the integration scheme. We used the additional data sequences acquired in some of the
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rooms and trained SVM-DAS on the outputs of the uni-modal models tested on these data.

The PeopleBot robot platform shown in Figure 3 was used for data acquisition and the final experiment. The robot was equipped with a SICK laser range finder and Videre STH-MDCS2 stereo head (only one of the cameras was used). The images were acquired at the resolution of 320x240 pixels. The whole system was implemented in the CAST (The CoSy Architecture Schema Toolkit, [CAST]) framework and run on a standard 2.5GHz dual-core laptop. The processing for both modalities was executed in parallel using both of the CPU cores.

7.2 Experimental Procedure and Results

Three days after the training data were collected, we performed a live experiment in the lab on the 2nd floor in the same building. The experiment was conducted during the day during sunny weather. The part of the environment that was explored by the robot consisted of 2 offices (Nick's office and Jeremy's office), a corridor and a meeting room. The interiors of the rooms and the influence of illumination can be seen in the images in Figure 13b. Automatically generated map of the environment is presented in Figure 14.

During the experiment, the task of the robot was to build a map and semantically label the navigation graph nodes and areas. The only knowledge given to the robot before the experiment consisted of the models of the three place classes: "office", "corridor" and "meeting room". As stated in Section 5, every time the robot created or revisited a node, the accumulated beliefs about the semantic category of the area were used to label the node and saved as a future prior. The label was also propagated to the whole area. We used detected doors to assign nodes to areas.

The whole experiment was videotaped and a video presenting the experimental setup, the test run and visualization of the obtained results can be found in in Extension 2. The

Figure 14: Final map obtained after the test run. The navigation graph is overlaid on the metric map and the color of the circles around the graph nodes indicate the place class assigned to each area bounded by detected doors. The system correctly labeled all the areas in the environment.

robot started in the Nick's office, and was manually driven through the corridor to Jeremy's office. Then, it was taken to the meeting room where the autonomous exploration mode was turned on. The robot used a frontier-based algorithm based on [Yamauchi, 1997]. Laser data was limited to 2m distance in the exploration to make sure that the robot not just perceived how the environment looked but also covered it to build the navigation graph. After the meeting room was explored, the robot was manually driven back to the Nick's office where the experiment finished. A video presenting visualization of the full test run is available in Extension 4. The labeling process was running on-line and the place classification was performed approximately at the rate of 5 times per second. The final semantic map build during the run is shown in Figure 14. We can see that the system correctly labeled all the areas in the environment.

The sensory data acquired during the test run were recorded and are available as Exten-

Figure 15: Place classification results obtained on the dataset recorded during the test run.

The first three bar charts show the results separately for each place class: “corridor”, “meeting room” and “office”. The charts show the percentage of the samples that were properly classified (most left bars marked with thick lines), but also how the misclassifications were distributed. The chart on the right presents the percentage of properly classified samples during the whole run. The two top rows give results for single modalities, while the bottom row shows results for the multi-modal system.

sion 6. Moreover, a video presenting the sequence of images and laser scans is presented in Extension 5. The fact that the data were stored allowed for additional performance analysis of the multi-modal place classification system, similar to the one presented in Section 6. The results are displayed in Figure 15. When we look at the overall classification rate for all the data samples in the test sequence, we see that vision significantly outperformed laser in this experiment (66% v.s. 84%). Still, the performance of the system was boosted by additional 8% compared to vision alone when the two modalities were integrated. The gain is even more apparent if we look at the detailed results for each of the classes (the first three charts in Figure 15). We see that the modalities achieved different performance, but also different error patterns, for each class. Clearly, the system based on laser range data is a very good corridor detector. On the other hand, vision was able to distinguish between the offices and the meeting room almost perfectly. Finally, the integrated system always achieved the performance of the more reliable modality and for two out of three classes outperformed the

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8 uni-modal systems. As can be seen in the video in Extension 2 and 4, this provided stable
9 performance for each of the classes and a robust base for the semantic labeling system.
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12 13 14 **8 Conclusions** 15

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17 This paper addressed the problem of place classification for topological localization and se-
18 mantic knowledge extraction in robotic systems. This is an important and challenging task,
19 where multiple sensor modalities are necessary in order to achieve generality and robustness,
20 and enable systems to work in realistic settings. To this end, we presented a new cue inte-
21 gration method able to combine multiple cues derived by a single modality, as well as cues
22 obtained by multiple sensors. The method was thoroughly tested in off-line experiments on
23 realistic data collected under varying conditions and as part of a real-time system running
24 on a robotic platform. The results obtained using multiple visual cues alone, and combined
25 with laser range features, clearly show the value of our approach. Finally, we showed that
26 the system can successfully be applied for the space labeling problem where it can be used
27 to augment the internal space representation with semantic place information.
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40 In the future, we plan to extend this method and attack the scalability issue, with par-
41 ticular attention to indoor office environments. These are usually characterized by a large
42 number of rooms with very similar features; we expect that in such a domain our approach
43 will be particularly effective. Another important aspect of place classification is the intrinsic
44 dynamics in the sensory information: as rooms are used daily, furniture is moved around,
45 objects are taken in and out of drawers and people appears. All of this affects the sensor
46 inputs of places in time. We plan to combine our approach with incremental extensions of
47 the SVM algorithm [Luo et al., 2007; Orabona et al., 2007] and to extend these methods from
48 fully supervised to semi-supervised learning, so to obtain a system able to learn continuously
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10 11 12 **Acknowledgment** 13

14
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